

Effect of *Moringa Oleifera* Leaf Extract on Testosterone Level of Male Wistar Rats Exposed to Petroleum Products

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Received November 15, 2023, Accepted December 5, 2023, Published December 20, 2023

The aim of this study was to investigate the effect of *Moringa oleifera* leaf extract on Testosterone levels of male Wistar rats exposed to Petrol, Diesel and Kerosene. Twenty-one (21) adults male Wistar rats were randomly divided into seven (7) groups, A to G, comprising three rats each. Group A was exposed to Petrol only for eight (8) weeks, Group B was exposed to Petrol for eight (8) weeks and later treated with *Moringa oleifera* leaf extract at 40 mg/kg/rat for two (2) weeks, Group C was exposed to Diesel only for eight (8) weeks, Group D was exposed to Diesel for eight (8) weeks and later treated with *Moringa oleifera* leaf extract at 40 mg/kg/rat for two (2) weeks, Group E was exposed to Kerosene only for eight (8) weeks, Group F were exposed to Kerosene for eight (8) weeks and later treated with *Moringa oleifera* leaf extract at 40 mg/kg/rat for two (2) weeks and Group G was exposed to *Moringa oleifera* leaf extract only at 40 mg/kg/rat to serve as positive control. Blood samples were collected through cardiac puncture into plain sample bottles which were centrifuged at 3000 revolutions per minute for five minutes and the serum was collected for biochemical analysis to determine the Testosterone level using AccuBind® Testosterone kit. The rats were exposed to the petroleum products using modified human nebulizer nose inhalation exposure method at the dose rate of 0.008 cm³/min/rat. There was statistically significant increase in serum Testosterone level in the groups exposed to Petrol, Diesel and Kerosene (Group A, B, C, D, E and F) which was returned to normal range following treatment with *Moringa oleifera* leaf extract (Group B, D and F). The results indicate that: *Moringa oleifera* leaf extract has ameliorative effect on Testosterone levels of Wistar rats exposed to petroleum products.

Keywords: Wistar Rat, *Moringa oleifera* Leaf Extract, Petrol, Diesel, Kerosene, Testosterone.

INTRODUCTION

Testes are paired organs usually ovoid in shape but considerably compressed from side to side, they are the primary organs of reproduction in male. They are situated in the inguinal region, enclosed in a diverticulum of abdomen called Scrotum (Abiaezute *et al.*, 2020). Testosterone is the major androgenic steroid hormone produced primarily in the Leydig cells, it has both intra-testicular effects (on spermatogenesis) and peripheral

effects (on accessory sex organs as well as non-reproductive organs such as Muscle, Bone, and Skin to name a few (Shantanam *et al.*, 2018). *Moringa oleifera* is a fast-growing, drought-resistant tree of the family Moringaceae, native to the Indian subcontinent (Cabi, 2019). It is widely cultivated for its young seed pods and leaves, use as vegetables and for traditional herbal medicine as well as for water purification (Sofowora *et al.*, 2013). A lot of publications have reported some of the specific effects of *Moringa oleifera* leaf extract on some body tissues or organs (Hassan *et al.*, 2020). It has an impressive range of medicinal uses, as various parts of it

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such as the Leaves, Roots, Seed, Bark, Fruit, Flowers and immature Pods act as cardiac and circulatory stimulants, possess antitumor, antipyretic, antiepileptic, anti-inflammatory, antiulcer, antispasmodic, diuretic, antihypertensive, cholesterol lowering, antioxidant, antidiabetic, hepatoprotective, antibacterial and antifungal activities, and are being employed for the treatment of different ailments in the ethno-medicine, particularly in South Asia (Patil *et al.*, 2020). Infertility and associated reproductive problems could be due to changes in hormonal levels that could be associated with exposure to petroleum products. Low sperm count and decrease sperm viability that is affecting reproductive performance among individuals might be due changes in testosterone level that could result from exposure to petroleum products.

This study is aimed to determine the effect of exposure to petroleum products on the Testosterone level and the ameliorative effect of *Moringa oleifera* in male Wister rats.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Area

The experiment was carried out in the Department of Veterinary Physiology and Biochemistry, Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto, Sokoto State. The state lies between latitude 13° 3' 490N, longitude 5° 14' 890E and at an altitude of 272 m above the sea level (Nata, 2009). The state shares common borders with Niger Republic to the North, Kebbi State to the South and Zamfara State to the East (Bello *et al.*, 2014). The state falls in the dry Sahel surrounded by sandy Sudan type Savannah (Jibrillah *et al.*, 2018).

Study Design

Experimental study was conducted and random sampling technique was employed. A total of 21 adults male Wistar rats were grouped into seven groups comprising of three rats in each and designated as group A to G.

Group A: exposed to Petrol only for eight (8) weeks

Group B: exposed to Petrol for eight (8) weeks and later treated with *Moringa oleifera* leaf extract for two (2) weeks.

Group C: exposed to Diesel only for eight (8) weeks

Group D: exposed to Diesel for eight (8) weeks and later treated with *Moringa oleifera* leaf extract for two (2) weeks.

Group E: exposed to Kerosene only for eight (8) weeks

Group F: exposed to Kerosene for eight (8) weeks and later treated with *Moringa oleifera* leaf extract for two (2) weeks.

Group G: exposed to *Moringa oleifera* leaf extract only

for eight (8) weeks to serve as positive control.

Extraction of Plant Material

Moringa oleifera leaves were obtained from Nakasari area, Sokoto south, Sokoto, Nigeria. The leaves were thoroughly rinsed with tap water to remove any residual dirt, air dried at room temperature for two to three weeks and then crushed into powdered form using mortar and pestle. 0.5kg (500g) of the grinded plant material was soaked into two liters of methanol and four liters of distilled water which was kept at room temperature free of dust for three days. It was sieved using soft cotton cloths and kept for seven days at room temperature for partial ethanol evaporation followed by 50°C using rotary evaporator and subsequently freeze dried. The yield of the freeze-dried sample representing the aqueous extract was obtained.

Acclimatization of Experimental Animals

Twenty-one (21) adult male Wistar rats (4-10 weeks) weighing between 120-200g were obtained from Faculty of Pharmaceutical sciences, Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto.

They were housed in cages and maintained in a room under environmental condition, with free access to water and feed. They were acclimatized for two weeks before the experiment commences.

Exposure to Petroleum Products

Petroleum products used for this study were purchased from NNPC filling station beside Federal Government College Sokoto, Sokoto south LGA, Sokoto State in separate containers which were used for this study. A modified human nebulizer nose inhalation exposure method (Azeez *et al.*, 2017) was used at 0.008cm³/min/rat.

Administration of Plant Material

A cannula attached to the 5 milliliters syringe was used in administration of the *Moringa oleifera* extract at the dose rate of 40 mg/kg/rat, while the rats were properly restraint using scrubbing method.

Determination of Testosterone Concentration

After exposure period of eight weeks, and treatment for two weeks, 2ml of blood sample was collected through cardiac puncture in to plain sample bottles which was centrifuged at 3000 revolutions per minute for five minutes and the serum was collected for biochemical analysis to determine the Testosterone level with AccuBind® Testosterone kit using Enzyme Immunoassay, Colorimetric method, which has Competi-

Table 1: effect of Petrol, Diesel and Kerosene and ameliorative effects *Moringa oleifera* leaf extract on Testosterone level of male Wistar rats. (N=21).

Parameters	A	B	C	D	E	F	G
Testosterone(ng/ml)	5.03±0.5ad	0.39±0.3ad	0.19±0.05bd	1.50±0.5bd	0.83±0.5cd	1.79±0.3cd	2.00±0.7d

Key: A (Petrol only), B (Petrol + *Moringa oleifera* leaf extract), C (Diesel only), D (Diesel + *Moringa oleifera* leaf extract), E (Kerosene only), F (Kerosene + *Moringa oleifera* leaf extract) and G (*Moringa oleifera* leaf extract (positive control)). Data is given as means ± standard deviation. abcd means in a row with different superscripts differ significantly (P <0.05).

-tive and Streptavidin-Coated plate principle.

Statistical Analysis

The data obtained was analyzed using InVivoStat Software (version 4.2) using Summary Statistics. Where statistical difference exists, Behrens Fisher test was used to separate the mean.

RESULTS

Table 4.1 below shows the effect of Petrol, Diesel and Kerosene and ameliorative effects *Moringa oleifera* leaf extract on Testosterone level of male Wistar rats. There was statistically significant difference (P <0.05) between the control group (group G) and the groups exposed to the petroleum products (group A, B, C, D, E and F). Moreover, there was statistically significant difference (P <0.05) between the group exposed to Petrol only (group A) and the group treated with *Moringa oleifera* leaf extract after exposure to Petrol (group B). There was statistically significant difference (P <0.05) between the group exposed to Diesel only (group C) and the group treated with *Moringa oleifera* leaf extract after exposure to Diesel (group D). And there was also statistically significant difference (P <0.05) between the group exposed to Kerosene only (group E) and the group treated with *Moringa oleifera* leaf extract after exposure to Kerosene (group F).

DISCUSSION

This study was aimed at determining changes in Testosterone levels of Wistar rats exposed to Petrol, Diesel and Kerosene and the ameliorative effect of *Moringa oleifera* leaf extract on the rats. Upon exposure of groups; A, C and E, to Petrol, Diesel and Kerosine for eight (8) weeks via inhalation, a marked increase in serum Testosterone level was observed. This is similar to the work of (Njoroge *et al.*, 2015). This may be due to ability of Benzene, Toluene, and Xylene in inducing oxidative stress as reported by (Zhou *et al.*, 2011). Also, after exposure of group B, D, and F to Petrol, Diesel and Kerosine for eight (8) weeks and later treated with *Moringa oleifera* leaf extract for two (2) weeks, Testosterone level was observed to be within the normal

range. This may be due to the powerful antioxidant effect of *Moringa oleifera*, as reported by (Hassan *et al.*, 2020). Moreover, it illustrated that the presence of flavonoids in *Moringa oleifera* leaf extract have a role in altering androgen levels.

CONCLUSION

The result of this study has shown that exposure of Wistar rats to Petroleum products through inhalation, causes marked increase in serum Testosterone levels. And treatment with *Moringa oleifera* leaf extract showed promising result.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Exposure of humans and animals to Petroleum products should be avoided or minimized. Humans with daily exposure to Petroleum products should include *Moringa oleifera* leaves in their food regimen.

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